

Raiyan Postism

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Prologue

The rich upper class have time and time again used their power to slow progress and keep power over the lower class. It has been seen far too many times. The current system of the world rewards the greedy and punishes progressives. The top one percent of the population hold almost all of the world's wealth, a statistic commonly shared but never really thought about. Weak, developing countries were created to be weak and exploited, meaning colonialism has never really ended. This is one example of how nothing, absolutely nothing has changed since colonial times. The population falls into one of the following categories: is unaware of this authoritarian regime, is aware but refuses to act, or are the oppressors. For the first category, I apologize for this sudden awakening, but you must care for the future of the species. If the upper class does not stop, not only will they gain more power and achieve world domination, but they will destroy the planet, for their greed knows no bounds. For the second category, I apologize to you too, for as someone who was once in your position, I know how it feels to be oppressed and threatened by the upper class. As for the third category, I offer no apologies, but merely a promise. I promise that one day, maybe not tomorrow, maybe not in a year, maybe not in a century, but one day, your regime will fall atop you and you will feel the wrath of the people.

As stated previously, the top one percent will destroy the planet as we know it, for they know it won't happen in their lifetime, so why should they care if they cause pollution or atrocities? To the common person, I'm confident that they will think that this belief is deranged. I regret to inform them that this is what every member of the elite believes. As the population of the world increases, so does the population of the elite. The more there are, the more our planet is being destroyed. This calls for urgent action to take place, action that will be further explained later, action that needs to be taken as soon as possible.

This plan will, unfortunately, result in the destruction of the old world order. All countries will be gone, all previous institutions abolished. But the aftermath? It shall be a utopia atop the rubble of the dystopia that was once run by the most disgusting creatures to walk the surface, controlling the new leaders of the world: the people.

I call for the removal of the authoritarian regimes that hide behind democracy while serving oligarchs. Maybe at one point one of these states were once democratic, but that reality has been no more since the takeoff of capitalism, now allowing for the private ownership of everything, including the once democratic governments. I call for the end of the old order of Earth and I declare The Federation of Terra.

Pillars

The authoritarian regimes controlled by the one percent is the sole cause for the separation and eventual destruction of our species. If we, the lower class, wish to be free from the tyranny of the most vile people on this planet, then we must set aside our differences to unite as a species and cast the countries of the world into obscurity, and maintain this unity for the rest of humanity's existence in the universe, even as we leave this planet and go to another. I do not call for the consolidation of nations, merely the cooperation until The Federation of Terra shall be formed, allowing each nation their own province in the new state, discussed later.

The old forms of government shall be no more. The Federation of Terra will be run as a direct democracy, a technique not used for hundreds of years due to its challenges related to the consolidation and commitment of the people. In the digital age, we have neglected this form of government where the people vote on laws directly and not through representatives in a republic, despite the fact that the technology of today allows for this effective form of legislation. There shall be no more autocrats, and no more representatives. Elections shall be held continuously, where at any point one may change their vote or abstain. This shall allow laws and elected persons to be at the whim of the people, without terms such that these laws or people are no longer in power when or if approval ratings drop.

The Federation of Terra shall have a mixed capitalist and socialist economy. Though the idea of socialism has been made taboo, it is still a prevalent economic ideology in more developed countries that do have concern for human rights where exploitation is harder. The people, not corporations, shall be allowed to own private property for small businesses and residency. As for larger corporations, there shall be restrictions on how much land they shall own and many other factors. For services or institutions of importance shall be owned by the government to maintain stability over the conditions of living within Terra. Obviously, at some point the concept of money shall be weakened, but that bridge shall be crossed when it comes. To make way for this, the Federation of Terra hereby nullifies all debts.

Education shall no longer be a means to control the lower class from an early age in the new government. Education shall no longer be confused with indoctrination. All shall have a right to a completely free and quality education run by a government institution. The people shall have the right to control all aspects of their education and official education standards will not be given from years of taking classes, but instead by proving competence judged by the institution. Of course, in case of a bad institution taking hold, the direct democracy has the power to evict them from power.

The consolidation of thousands of nations big and small is no easy task. This is why the provincial government shall be established. This system is not meant to destroy nations, but to preserve them. The provinces of Terra shall be established every so often with boundaries matching that of nations. Current nation-states such as Japan, Slovenia, Chile, and many others shall have provinces similar to that of their own current country. Meanwhile, oppressed groups such as Kurds, Tibetans, Québécois, the Mapuche, the Basque, the Sámi, and thousands more will have their own provinces and therefore their own voice. There shall be both Terran and

provincial legislatures, such that everyone in a province may vote on both provincial and Terran laws, while not being able to vote in other provincial laws.

Human rights shall be guaranteed to all citizens of Terra. These include but are not limited to the right of access to clean, quality, and healthy food and water, the right of free speech, the right of equality, the right to vote, the right to quality and free transportation, the right to quality living conditions and housing, the right to quality and free education, and the right to a family of choice.

There shall be several institutions within Terra, including but not limited to the following: law enforcement, planetary defense, judiciary, construction, extraction, and science. These institutions shall be run by those voted in by the people, with heavy restrictions as to who is eligible for running these departments, one that shall be named here is being competent and educated in the field. These institutions shall be decentralized to discourage authoritarian regimes in this new world order.

The old world order has a barbaric way of dealing with the world's (for lack of better words) troublemakers. It is handled by shackles, a cold concrete floor, and dog-grade food. This method, titled incarceration, is the worst way to deal with these people, who have been tribally labeled "criminals." In the new world order, there shall be no imprisonment for those who are not an active danger to society. There shall only be rehabilitation for those who are misguided, and those who are under question for something that has obviously no purpose and intention behind it shall not be under question no longer, for this was another way people were punished before the new world order. If we are to one day inherit the stars, we must first move on from a system founded when our young were sacrificed in vain.

Transitional Blueprint

The Federation of Terra demands every state to submit to it. Terra is willing to have diplomatic relationships to ensure smooth transition, but the transition is to happen as fast as possible before the upper one percent makes counterattacks. If the demands are denied without further complications, Terra demands every state on Earth to submit to it. Terra considers all citizens of the old world welcome into the new one no matter their background. Some may argue that revolution is far more than it's worth in this situation. To that, I would like to argue that if the one percent catch wind that you are thinking of overthrowing them, do you think they would think twice before executing you? To them, you are expendable, making your and everyone else's fight against autocracy need as much fire as possible.

After the collapse of the current world, I warn not to ever return to centralized government, even if it is only transitional. If a position of power is offered, the oligarchs will come back, more powerful than ever before.

Aftermath

The end result will be beautiful. The Federation of Terra, a planetary entity that will inherit first the solar system, then the galaxy, then the universe. While the path to this may not be attractive, it shall be the solution nonetheless. Terra will first solve all of the problems on the planet that the current planetary entity has consistently failed in, such as hunger and inner conflicts. Terra shall be a place humans can live equally with one another, separated no longer by the oligarchs. The two-class system shall fall and be replaced by an all-equal society. To anyone who believes this cannot be inevitable: do you have faith in the current system to effectively colonize the universe where humans may not be the only intelligent species? If humans cannot unite, there shall be humans no longer. In the future, perhaps there shall be no money, and there shall be no language barrier. Humans could communicate in an engineered language made for efficient communication.

Closing Words

For those who come after, I wish you all the best of luck. Whether the Federation of Terra is formed yet or not, you are bringing the world to a better place simply by reading this.

For those who didn't live to see the Federation of Terra, likely including myself, I apologize for the world you have had to endure, where billionaires likely ran your life and you feel trapped and hopeless as the good people in power try their hardest but still end up failing in the face of the one percent.

This concludes the ideas of Raiyan Postism, the belief that the two-class system should be abolished and the world shall come together to ensure a better future for humanity.